

EULAC
MUSEUMS

Project Testimonies

“The results of the EU-LAC-MUSEUMS project will benefit the worldwide museum community and their communities. I hope that this successful project will have the opportunity to be extended to other regions.”

President of the International Council of Museums (ICOM)

29 April 2019, Policy Round Table at the European Commission, Brussels, Belgium

“Though many miles lie between them and us we all are brought together through our shared passion for music, dance, art and community spirit.

The exchange changed me as a person in so many ways. It made me proud of my island background, improved my confidence and gave me skills which will stay with me forever.

I want to stay in Skye, really make a difference to the island, challenge tourism and retain our way of life for both locals and visitors, like the way the Boruca community does.”

Young Person from the Isle of Skye

16 September 2017, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“For me, and Boruca, this experience has been a dream because we’ve not only learnt about our indigenous history and culture, we shared it with other young people from Scotland and Portugal, we’ve learnt to respect our culture, I feel more proud about Boruca, our people, our land and our language.”

Young Person from Bourca, Costa Rica

9 March 2018, “Memory and community museums: the right to self-determination and the role of young people” Conference, Bourca, Costa Rica

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Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

16 September 2017, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“I feel this exchange has changed me ... it has made me more confident... now I can speak to my whole school and community. Before the exchange I didn't really pay attention to my surroundings, our nature, our landscape the world challenges around me, now ... it has made me think further about my community and our way of life.”

Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

16 September 2017, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“We were able to witness a great blossoming in our six young Skye people. ...(they) came so far out of their shells that it was palpable [...] (they) had truly meaningful, memorable, educational and life-changing experiences. [...] During each successive workshop, it was evident that the aims were bearing fruit. Without the EU-LAC-MUSEUMS project, they would not have had these experiences.

Community leader and Ecomuseum Board Member from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

15 November 2019, Letter, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“I want to stay in Skye, really make a difference to the island, challenge tourism and retain our way of life for both locals and visitors, like the way the Bourca community does.”

Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

16 September 2017, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“Our culture was left aside and we stopped practising it, we try to avoid it and we are sometimes ashamed by it. Also, technology and drugs have affected us and our lack of interest in our culture. [...] I feel very grateful for this project because it has allowed us to rescue all these things that were unknown to us, and the talks with the elderly, have been helpful to us, and knowing how the things were in the past, how the community was organised in the past and the real origin of our culture, how it has evolved and how we can take it forward.”

Young Person from Bourca, Costa Rica

9 March 2018, “Memory and community museums: the right to self-determination and the role of young people” Conference, Bourca, Costa Rica

“As an older person, as the museum’s founder and representative of the community, this is unforgettable, and these words are engraved in my mind [...] this great project which is a great blessing. [...] Many thanks for this opportunity.”

Community Elder from Bourca, Costa Rica

9 March 2018, “Memory and community museums: the right to self-determination and the role of young people” Conference, Bourca, Costa Rica

“Mark the path of our organisation’s actions and missions in the next three years.”

Speaker representing International Council of Museums (ICOM) from the discussions regarding ICOM Resolution on Museums, Communities and Sustainability.

7 September 2019, ICOM Summit “Museums as Cultural Hubs: The Future of Tradition”, Kyoto, Japan

“Both academic, reinforcing the importance of the 1972 Round Table of Santiago de Chile for museums in the 21st Century, and provides advice to community members considering the creation of a new museum or similar heritage institution. The contributing authors are all world leaders in the field.”

Presidents of the regional committees for Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) from the International Council of Museums (ICOM)

3 September 2019, ICOM Summit “Museums, Communities and Sustainability” workshop, Kyoto, Japan

“We don't want this craftsmanship to die, it's our tradition, we have had so many bad times in Curré, we must pass it down to the young people, just like my father and grandfather did to me, we must keep our culture alive!”

Community Elder from Rey Curré, Costa Rica

17 February 2018, Interview, Rey Curré, Costa Rica

“That relationship [between culture and tourism] is very... it’s necessary for both fields. Let’s say, they’re closely related, because nowadays in this globalized world, in this globalized times, we’ll always need resources to highlight a culture. To be precise, we aren’t selling – and I would like to clarify that right now – we’re not selling culture, we’re not selling our culture. Rather, we’re promoting ourselves so we don’t lose our culture. So people won’t say that ‘they don’t exist, they don’t; look, so far I haven’t seen anything [about the Boruca people].’

Principal Head Teacher from Rey Curré, Costa Rica

17 February 2018, Interview, Rey Curré, Costa Rica

“We’re promoting ourselves to show what little we have to the world, [to show] that we still exist. Therefore, tourism and tourists should understand that’s one characteristic of the people, of the community, of the Costa Rican origins and the Boruca culture, which in this case is our group. And logically, we do make use of resources. Resources for what? For turning around our situation. And how do we turn it around? By getting the tourists to take with them their piece of work, their craft, their decorations, that – look, it enriches us, but not so much for the value of a painting, of a mask, of a jícaro, but because [people get to realise] ‘look, there’s something, there’s a Boruca craft, there’s a Boruca detail!’ And of course, we’re also saying that the artisans earn very little. Artisans only get a round of applause for their efforts, and that’s no sustenance. So there will always be an interaction, there’s always the need for both things.”

Principal Head Teacher from Rey Curré, Costa Rica

17 February 2018, Interview, Rey Curré, Costa Rica

“It’s been a really great experience because I’ve met lots of people and I’ve made lots of friendships, and thanks to them I felt comfortable in an environment where I could express who I am; I’m an indigenous person, I like being who I am, and I’m very proud of it. I’m proud to be indigenous and from Boruca. I’m always learning more about who I am and where the European young people are from.”

Young Person from Bourca, Costa Rica

9 March 2018, “Memory and community museums: the right to self-determination and the role of young people” Conference, Bourca, Costa Rica

“The community of Boruca will always be with me. There were so many warm-hearted people that welcomed us into their way of life, guiding us through their land, the chance to make traditional masks and learning about the Brunka language from elders. I know I have come out of this exchange as a much stronger and more independent person, and understand how important it is to keep our culture, our Gaelic language alive! I feel like now I can do anything!!”

Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

16 September 2017, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“The youth exchange has given me an opportunity to understand my community of Barcelos, where we have come from and where we are going as a community. I have met community leaders and got to understand why our community is so famous for pottery. It was an honour to welcome the Costa Ricans to Portugal and to be in their community. We shared not just daily life together, but music, food, and language!

I even performed along with my music group to the Costa Ricans, I was nervous, but this programme has given me the strength to be confident!”

Young Person from Porto, Portugal

7 July 2018, Youth Exchange Workshop, Porto, Portugal

“I am very grateful for the friendships that resulted through the exchange. Of the things I learned, I feel that the most important is to value and respect the different ways of life in all our communities.

Our history, our heritage is different, but we are all the same, facing the same problems.”

Young Person from Porto, Portugal

7 July 2018, Youth Exchange Workshop, Porto, Portugal

“I’m not quite sure how, to sum up, my experience in Costa Rica. It was amazing. Exhausting. Life changing. Exciting. Hot. Incredible. A great learning experience.

The trip changed me in many ways. Before I would have described myself as a relatively shy, quiet and introverted person and I’ll be the first to admit that my communication skills and confidence are something I struggled with. This exchange really brought me out my shell and exposed a fun side of my personality that some people don’t see. I feel more confident about myself, my dreams and aspirations the future and understanding the ways in which we can sustain our community for the future.”

Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

16 September 2017, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“For me, and Boruca, this experience has been a dream because we’ve not only learnt about our indigenous history and culture, we have shared it with other young people from Scotland and Portugal, we’ve learnt to respect our culture, I feel more proud about Boruca, our people, our land and our language. This exchange has given both me and Boruca to chance to go global, tell our stories, learn other stories and most importantly how to be respectful and value it. Otherwise one day we may lose our culture and our traditions, and as young people, we have to be responsible with the knowledge and memories of each our places.”

Young Person from Bourca, Costa Rica

9 July 2019, Youth Exchange Discussion, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“I feel this exchange has changed me in so many ways, these changes have all been good, it has made me more confident; before I wasn’t really someone who liked to speak in front of an audience but now I can speak to my whole school and community.

The experience has also changed the way I look at things. Before the exchange I didn’t really pay attention to my surroundings, our nature, our landscape the world challenges around me, now after being part of the programme it has made me think further about my community and our way of life. The young people and community of Rey Curre are the best people I have ever met.”

Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

16 September 2017, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“The youth exchange built around the ‘Our Vision of Change’ program, was an extremely rewarding experience for us, the team of the Union of Community Museum in Oaxaca, Mexico and many of the participants of the Community Museum Network of America.

[...] They shared their experiences of dialogue with elders and their heightened appreciation of community memory. Indirect and sincere individual testimonies, they recorded their hopes that other youths and community members continue this significant engagement with the practices and beliefs of their ancestors.”

International Expert on Community Museums

9 March 2018, Interview, “Memory and community museums: the right to self-determination and the role of young people” Conference, Bourca, Costa Rica

“Being able to share São João da Madeira's history with the Costa Ricans was an honour, and being welcomed into the homes of the Costa Ricans was a chance to really see we are all the same.

I will always remember the fun we had sharing Portuguese dancing and music, helping everyone learn the moves. I loved it!

Throughout this exchange, I started building my experience by volunteering at the Museu de Chapelaria. The programme and facilitators helped me find the courage to gain skills needed for my future.”

Young Person from Porto, Portugal

7 July 2018, Youth Exchange Workshop, Porto, Portugal

“I’ve become more aware of where I live, how lucky I am to live where I live – the things I’ve got like my Gaelic, my ability to play the pipes and just my culture and the history of this place where we live. How lucky we are to live here and to have had the opportunity to share it with others which has made me want to travel in the future to be able to share again and see other cultures.”

Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

20 September 2018, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“We shared the differences which is like how different the climate is, how different the wildlife is, the bugs, the food in particular and our music is very different as well. [...] we also shared the similarities so the influence of tourism as well was a big thing and how we don’t want our communities to be ruined by over tourism, but we also want to welcome everyone. [...]”

Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

20 September 2018, Youth Exchange Evaluation Workshop, Isle of Skye, Scotland

"[...] Having being brought up through the medium of Scottish Gaidhlig I have been fortunate enough to have been made aware of the value of our local culture and identity throughout my childhood however it was during the youth exchange where I was first encouraged to think about my community on a global scale. By comparing, contrasting and sharing our cultural heritage, intangible cultural heritage in particular, it became apparent to us all that though many miles lie between them and us, we are all brought together through our shared passion for music, dance and community spirit. It made me realise the importance of my heritage while also highlighting its fragility in our increasingly globalised world. The vulnerable nature of our heritage became the topic of many meetings, both abroad and back home in Skye leading us as a group to look into methods to help protect our language, music and oral traditions such as attending workshop ran by Samuel Franco Arce on safeguarding cultural heritage in times of crisis. [...] The experience of the youth exchange and the gained knowledge on community heritage made me feel confident that I could successfully contribute to discussions in a way I would not have been able to before. Before the youth exchange I was generally quite introverted and majorly lacked in confidence, so much so that I nearly did not apply for the project. The combination of the leadership exercises at workshops and being put out of my comfort zone during the exchange radically changed my self-confidence, leading me to do things that I would never have imagined I would have been able to do a year or two previously. [...] I have also become much more proud of my island background and am now passionate about sharing and protecting my island heritage and culture, particularly traditional art, leading to me to begin studying an MA in History of Art at the University of Edinburgh in September 2019. In future years I am hope to use my degree to possibly go into the community heritage sector and hopefully reinvest my experiences into developing projects such as the Ceumannan Eco museum in Staffin, Skye."

Young Person from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

8 September 2020, Letter, Isle of Skye, Scotland

“We want our children to place value on what is on their doorstep...It was like being thrown a rope, unsure if we should catch it at first....

But we are so glad we caught it...as the young people are us tomorrow.”

Community leader and Ecomuseum Board Member from the Isle of Skye, Scotland

16 February 2019, Interview, Isle of Skye, Scotland